

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: YUNUS****FIRST NAME: ABDUL MANAF****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 15–23)
2. American English Vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 21–32)
3. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34–37)
4. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 58–66)
5. Sample Corrections to Papers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 66–71)
6. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6–14)

GOOD ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

It is always a struggle prior to beginning a challenge as this course, to have everything planned out rightly. This was the perfect state one was in prior to watching the video and subsequently reading and studying the orientation material (EUCLID 2021, 5) and the Period 1 resource for ACA-401D; this resource has been immensely beneficial in my ability to put this work together.

As all academic works are, one must read and understand before trying hands-on the assignment. The resource also gave an in-depth explanation of what a student needs to do and the basis a student I required to reach to be able to excel at the program of study. Required to provide a response paper on the Period 1 resource, I intend to focus on subject matters that benefitted me the most. The focus of the paper will be on the areas of punctuation; American English, and British English; plagiarism and its importance in academic work and how to avoid it; Latin abbreviations and expressions and how to use them; a look at how beneficial sample corrections provided by the resource was and is; and how to write essays (academic writings) (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8).

2) PUNCTUATIONS

In the process of producing good academic work, punctuation is key to communicating effectively with the examiner. The material dealt with all punctuation marks and gave examples of how to use each punctuation mark, the correct usage of the mark and wrong usage of same, as well as when to use each. Punctuation marks covered in the course material are commas, apostrophes, periods, hyphens, dashes, brackets (round brackets, square brackets, angle brackets, curly brackets), colons, semicolons, bullet points, ellipsis, full stops, exclamations, question marks, and quotation marks.

Focusing on a few of the punctuation, our first focus is the punctuation ellipsis. Ellipsis is used to indicate that some text is missing, usually from a quotation – do not surround with spaces and no need to use square brackets around ellipsis (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 22). Our second is the full stop. A full stop should not be used if it will be followed or preceded by an ellipsis (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 22). A full stop is used at the end of a sentence to signal the end of a sentence – a sentence that is not a question and not a command. The third and final focus is the punctuation mark - comma (,). The comma according to the resource is used:

to surround a non-defining clause (one which adds descriptive information but which can be removed without losing the meaning of the sentence) – note that only ‘which’ or ‘who’ can be used in this type of clause, not ‘that’ (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 19).

Beyond the above, the comma can, however, neither be used where defining information is used at the start of a sentence, nor can a comma be used to surround a defining clause that cannot be removed without losing the meaning of the sentence, nor can it be used to join main clauses linked by adverbial phrases or adverbs together (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 19).

3) AMERICAN ENGLISH VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

At this stage, the lesson is geared toward understanding the two (2) most popular and widely used English dialects in the world. This is the concept of focus in this section of the Response Paper (RP). There are British English and American English. The first difference was words with different pronunciations yet same spelling. For example, schedule, advertisement, clerk, renaissance, and many other fields (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25). The second were words with different spelling, yet the same pronunciation. For example, color – colour; license – licence; defense – defence; cheque – check; and many more (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25). Thirdly, words with the same term have different but similar spelling and pronunciation. For example, aluminium versus aluminum, maths versus math, and many other fields (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 26).

Also, the difference in dates between the two dialects where American English prefers to start with the month before the day and the year on the end, whilst British English uses the day before the month and then the month at the end (Cleenewerck and Gulma

2021, 31). Again, an important focus of the lesson was the use of commas, periods, and quotation marks. This section teaches that generally, with respect to phrases or sentences of focus, American English will put the sentence in quotation marks (double inverted commas "..."), whilst inverted commas are used in British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 31). For example, "The man carried the bag." (American English) 'The man carried the bag.' (British English). In cases where it is a quotation within a quotation, the full sentence takes the above dialect preference whilst the quotation in the middle takes the opposite of the dialect's preference (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 31, 32). For example, "They said: 'the man carried the bag' and went away. (American English) 'They said: "the man carried the bag" and went away.'

Our last focus here will be on punctuation on words for formal letters versus punctuations on words in informal writings. For example, Dear Mr. Yunus – this is American English writing. However, in British English, it will be written as Dear Mr Yunus (without the full stop after the Mr) (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 32).

4) PLAGIARISM

An integral aspect of academic writing is the need to credit persons and sources from which information is obtained. It is also common knowledge that facts that are widespread, such as the capital of Gambia being Banjul, do not need referencing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 37). Why must plagiarism be avoided in the first place? Plagiarism is a serious academic offense that can lead to serious consequences for offenders; unfair to take someone's work (intellectual property) without acknowledging them, and it is also wrong and unethical (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). Plagiarism, therefore is:

... when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34).

To avoid plagiarism, especially as a student or one working on academic writing, one must cite the author or source of information (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). This can be done in two (2) ways which are *in-text citation* – indicating the author(s), year of publication, date, page(s) etc. – and *list of works cited* – which provides full detail of the source, including publication, website link, edition, city of publication, issue number, etc. at the end of the work (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 35).

In using in-text citations, two (2) methods could be used – quotations and paraphrasing. In quoting, the text must be in quotation marks (""). However for texts that are over four (4) lines – known as a long quotation – they will take no quotation marks, and they will be dented to like little paragraphs on their own (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 35–36).

Yet, the use of quotations is discouraged unless an authority figure makes a particularly strong statement that can help one's academic work, or the quotation itself

contains a strong statement, because an over usage will make one's work look unnatural and as though not one's own research (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 36).

Paraphrasing, on the other hand, is writing information obtained from a source in a whole different way and in a different style, such as it does not resemble the original in style nor is it simply picking from books and sources (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 36).

5) **LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS**

Commonly used in many writings into legal, Latin expressions and abbreviations have been widely used by students all the way from basic school. However, in academic writings, Latin abbreviations are appropriate in the footnotes. Latin abbreviations are also useful for informal writing and communications and instead, the English meaning of these Latin abbreviations is appropriate for academic and formal writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 59).

The resource provided numerous examples of Latin abbreviations, their Latin meanings or expressions, and the corresponding English meanings. Some examples included very popular ones such as: *E.g.* - *exempli gratia* meaning for example, for instance; *Cv.* - *curriculum vitae* meaning curriculum vitae; *A.M.* - *ante meridiem* meaning before noon; *Etc.* - *et cetera* meaning and so on; and other people/things; *q.v.* - *quod vide* meaning which see; used to cross-refer to material that can be found elsewhere within the same book or piece of writing. *q.v.* is not synonymous with *cf.*; the latter cross-refers to external material; *v. inf.* meaning *vide infra* see below; and many others (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 59–64).

The Latin expressions are known to be appropriate for all writings but not the abbreviations.

6) **SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS**

A cursory look at this section of the resource provides details of how the Instructor will make corrections to the work of students (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 66). This section also gives a view of what the instructor will be looking out for in the response paper and to prepare a student not simply to understand a correction done to a work, but also to avoid the basic errors in the first place.

It also provides a structure of what a response paper looks like, and a practical view of the components of the response paper for the student to first make his or her own corrections before submitting work for review and grading (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 66–71).

7) ESSAY WRITING

As with all writings, grasping the basics of it is very important before entering the zone of details. The resource for Period 1 provided readers with how to write essays, more specifically academic writings before other details were brought in. This provided a means to better understand the resource and to tune the mind to be prepared for the details that followed the text and video (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7).

Before engaging in academic writings, in summary, one must have an idea in mind, and first read widely on the topic or subject matter before doing any form of writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). After researching on the subject matter, one should record some short notes or whatever is deemed fit to be recorded that would aid the work (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). Then the work should be planned and put into a structure following exactly how it should be presented.

Sources should be cited for all sources from which resource, facts, knowledge is obtained from indicating them either in the text (in-text referencing) or using footnotes, and at the end of the text in works cited (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 11). This prevents plagiarism as it is a great academic offence, and a means of sticking to best practice.

After work is completed, one should go over the work again, review it, give it to another person whether colleague or superior to proofread before final review and then submitted (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8). This will reduce as much error that is likely to be made in the work.

8) CONCLUSION

As beneficial as the resource has been, it has putting one in a position to be able to have the basics right in order to proceed diligently and competently during the period of study. With years to complete the program, it is good to have a very good start and a good grasp of the foundation tasks that would lead to significant improvement in scholarship both during and after completion of the course of study.

Footnotes have not been used in this work because footnotes are not used in response papers (Cleenewerck 2016).

The highest level of academic scholarship is the Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.), for persons not continuing with a field in academia, yet it is a stage that prepares one for literally every aspect of life and career. Research is essential to provide the innovation and advancement that society has without over the last decade. The ever-demanding society we find ourselves also need persons who are research inclined and can think outside the box. This first step is a very excellent platform to achieve and meet the expectations of oneself and society.

REFERENCES

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